

Journal of Religion & Society (JR&S)

Available Online:

<https://islamicreligious.com/index.php/Journal/index>

Print ISSN: [3006-1296](#) Online ISSN: [3006-130X](#)

Platform & Workflow by: [Open Journal Systems](#)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20743577>

From Education to Enterprise: Examining the Barriers Preventing Unemployed Graduates from Pursuing Entrepreneurship in Quetta

Naqib Ullah

M.Phil Scholar, Department of Social Work, University of Balochistan, Quetta

naqibkhan8877@gmail.com

Dr. Muhammad Yousuf

Lecturer / Research Supervisor, Department of Social Work, University of Balochistan, Quetta

usuf.barech@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship is an alternative strategy to reduce graduate unemployment and promoting economic development among unemployed university graduates. This study examined the barriers to entrepreneurship among unemployed graduates in Quetta city. The data were collected from 216 unemployed graduates through a structured questionnaire, the study employed a quantitative descriptive research design, Purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used to select respondents from major public universities in Quetta. The data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings indicated that lack of capital the most known barrier to unemployed graduates. Majority of the graduates considered that limited access to financial support and loans for business to create new businesses. The study also reported limited business knowledge and lack of practical entrepreneurial skills which reduce unemployed graduates from starting new businesses. Complicated government procedures and administrative requirements were identified as important barriers among graduates. Furthermore, the study lacks of support from family and market competitions depressed graduates from starting entrepreneurship as a career option. The study recommends vast entrepreneurship programs in Quetta city especially for students and graduates. Further the study recommends specific funds for students and graduates and publication of incubation centres in every university for a better access to entrepreneurship programs.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, Barriers, Graduate Unemployment, Employment, Financial Constraints, Quetta, Balochistan.*

Introduction

The process of finding possibilities, allocating resources, and taking chances in order to start and run a new business is known as entrepreneurship. Through their introduction of innovation, creation of jobs, and encouragement of market competition, entrepreneurs are essential to economic progress. They endure the risks of uncertainty while combining the factors of production land, labor, and capital to create commodities and services. Joseph Schumpeter highlighted the tight connection between innovation and entrepreneurship,

characterizing entrepreneurs as agents of "creative destruction," propelling economic advancement through novel concepts and technology (Schumpeter, 1934). According to contemporary viewpoints, successful entrepreneurs must possess qualities like risk-taking, innovation, and leadership (Peter F. Drucker, 1985). Education of entrepreneurship is widely promoted as a strategy to reduce graduate unemployment. To encourage entrepreneurial intention and skill development, universities all across the world have incorporated entrepreneurship courses into their curricula.

In a comprehensive study of entrepreneurship education, Nabi et al. (2018) discovered that although educational programs have a favourable impact on entrepreneurial intention, they do not always result in the development of businesses. The authors contend that practical exposure, mentorship, and experiential learning are essential for entrepreneurial success. Similarly, Kew et al. (2013) found that while young people who obtain entrepreneurship education are more likely to indicate interest in company start-ups, real implementation is limited by a lack of institutional and financial support.

Entrepreneurship education frequently stays theoretical in developing nations. According to Nawaz (2021), classroom-based education is prioritized above real-world business incubation in Pakistani colleges. Graduates lack confidence and practical skills in the absence of internships, industry participation, and business mentoring.

Limited industry-university cooperation in Quetta further undermines graduation readiness. Exposure to actual business contexts is diminished in the absence of incubation facilities. Therefore, research indicates that without systemic ecosystem support, entrepreneurship education is insufficient on its own. There is a growing push for entrepreneurship as a smart way to address graduates' unemployment. Initiatives at the national level have made an effort to promote self-employment through training programs and funding schemes. But in Quetta, graduates' actual involvement in entrepreneurial endeavours is still quite low. This implies that institutional, financial, sociocultural, and structural obstacles can be preventing entrepreneurial activity. Designing context-specific solutions instead of depending only on broad national policies requires an understanding of these obstacles. (Acs et al., 2018; Nabi et al., 2017) It is important to understand the socio-economic barriers, affecting entrepreneurs of Quetta's unemployed graduates. This study can improve and make it easy that how many people are engaged with entrepreneurship and how many are hindered by universities arrangements, support of family, skills and access to resources. More significantly, in Quetta and other Pakistani cities, it may guide evidence-based policies and focused interventions that support young entrepreneurship as a workable way to combat Unemployment effects the social life of graduates in Quetta and causes tensions frustration and worse health impacts as Well it also causes the dishonoured in society because now Wealth is becoming a key component of the economic structure. Unemployment is one of the biggest and the vital problem faced by the people in all over Pakistan. Dramatic increase in growth of high level of unemployment is significant worry for less-developed as well as developed countries. It's becoming the most crucial and critical issue encountered by the young of Balochistan

specifically the graduates. Quetta as the capital city of Balochistan is more at risk compare to the other cities. The study focuses on exploring the Socio-economic factors and barriers to entrepreneurship among unemployed University graduates of Quetta city. The research is limited who has completed their higher education in Quetta and remain unemployed. It looks at the socioeconomic factors that contribute to unemployment, how joblessness affects recent graduates' life, and what barriers keep them from launching their own businesses. In addition, the study intends to gather ideas and make recommendations to alleviate graduate unemployment and promote entrepreneurship. Unemployment is now considered the most challenging social problem in Balochistan and Quetta being its capital is facing backwardness due to joblessness this study is confined particularly to the unemployment among the graduates of Quetta. The study is limited to Quetta; it might not fully represent the realities of graduate's unemployment and hurdles to entrepreneurship in other parts of Balochistan.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework of the study titled "Socio-Economic Barriers to Entrepreneurship among Unemployed University Graduates in Quetta" describes the relationship between different socio- economic berries to entrepreneurship among unemployed graduates in Quetta. The framework indicates four main categories of barrier which are social barriers, Economic barriers, administrative barriers and Academic or Educational Barriers. The independent variables influence the willingness and ability of the unemployed graduates to make and sustain entrepreneurship start-ups. The dependent variable of the study is the objective of entrepreneurship and outcome, which refers to the readiness of graduates to start a successful business. The framework indicates that entrepreneurship can play a vital role to reduce unemployment and promote economic development. However, there are many barriers that prevent students from entrepreneurship journey. These obstacles affect their confidence, motivation and opportunities necessary for entrepreneurship creation. Therefore, understanding these obstacles is very much important for developing policies and entrepreneurship among unemployed university graduates.

Firstly, Social barriers are one of the major challenges faced by unemployed graduates. According to the framework, the graduates must secure government jobs rather than going for entrepreneurship. Families discourage the graduates to start their own businesses. In many societies government and private sector jobs are very prestigious than entrepreneurship. Another obstacle which is described in the framework is lack of support. Entrepreneurship needs encouragement and moral from families and friends. So, when this support is lacking then the graduates take risks and hesitate to start and run businesses.

Secondly economic obstacles are the most significant barriers among unemployed graduates. The framework indicates no proper policies from government to start successful entrepreneurship initiatives. No Financial support mechanism for graduates and no loans access. The framework further identifies lack of grants and financial assistance as a major problem. A lot of unemployed graduates have ideas but they cannot put is to start-up level due to financial constraints, which restrict entrepreneurs from starting their own businesses.

Thirdly administrative are the institutional and governmental obstacles that hinder graduate from entrepreneurial practices. The framework indicates lack of appropriate curriculum regarding entrepreneurship. Weak institutional support in terms of mentorship and guidance. Thirdly the framework indicates academic barriers which lack of practical training is the major obstacle. University education often provides theoretical knowledge, graduates do not access to practical training in business planning, management and entrepreneurial practices. Further limited access to BICs and NICS reduces graduates from receiving mentorship, training, networking and financial guidance. Weak entrepreneurship training programs are also contributing to lack of confidence and practical skills. Lastly the aim and outcome is the dependent variable in the framework, represented by willingness of graduates to make and start successful businesses. The framework indicated that when social, economic, administrative and academic barriers increase the starting of entrepreneurship decreases. And when reducing these obstacles can increase entrepreneurship.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Literature review

Entrepreneurship is becoming more likely known as an alternative way of employment. It indicates the process of generating, finding, and overseeing business ventures in order to produce revenue and jobs (World Bank, 2020). Educated youth are frequently seen to have a higher potential for becoming entrepreneurs (Nabi et al., 2018). However, young entrepreneurship is frequently facing obstacles such a lack of funding, inadequate institutional support, and constrictive cultural norms (Fatoki & Chindoga, 2011). One of the biggest obstacles to entrepreneurship worldwide is regularly shown is access to financing. Balochistan has lower levels of banking penetration than other regions, according to the State Bank of Pakistan (2021), indicating that financial inclusion is still uneven between provinces. Youth entrepreneurs are mostly facing problems while getting loans because they do not have

any assurance for repayment and credit record. Young people start-ups are looked by financial agencies as high danger investments (Fatoki and Chindoga, 2011). Regardless of Pakistan's introduction of loan program for young people, youth are discouraged by documentation necessities (Haque, 2021). Additionally, participation is reduced by limited awareness of these programs. The aims of microfinance organizations are to diminish financial problems. For a successful entrepreneurship journey, organizations need different sources of funding such as governmental, non-governmental organizations and investors (The World Bank, 2020). Financial accessibility is further hampered in Balochistan by inadequate banking infrastructure and a small number of investors. Financial obstacles continue to be a major issue in the literature on entrepreneurship. A lot of college graduates have academic knowledge but lack real-world business skills. The capacity of graduates to see market possibilities and run businesses successfully is diminished by inadequate entrepreneurship education programs. Self-confidence and entrepreneurial intention are positively impacted by entrepreneurship education. However, graduates' entrepreneurial readiness is diminished by insufficient hands-on training and poor university-industry ties. (Fayolle and Gailly, 2015)

Lack of Financial Access

Limited access to financial resources is one of the biggest obstacles to entrepreneurship. Many recent graduates don't have the personal funds and do not have access to get funds from banks as a loan. According to the OECD (2022), access to finance remains one of the biggest hurdles faced by entrepreneurs in developing economies. In a similar vein, Naudé (2010) contends that young people and low-income groups have fewer options to pursue entrepreneurship due to financial exclusion. Low business formation in Pakistan is also a result of inadequate microfinance institutions and a lack of venture capital.

Insufficient Knowledge and Experience in Entrepreneurship

Technical and problem-solving abilities are necessary for entrepreneurship. a lot of college graduates have academic knowledge but lack real-world business skills. The capacity of graduates to see market possibilities and run businesses successfully is diminished by inadequate entrepreneurship education programs. Fayolle and Gailly (2015) discovered that self-confidence and entrepreneurial intention are positively impacted by entrepreneurship education. However, graduates' entrepreneurial readiness is diminished by insufficient hands-on training and poor university-industry ties.

Administrative Barriers

New entrepreneurs are deterred by complicated business registration processes, copious documentation, and ineffective bureaucracy. Entrepreneurs encounter delays in licensing, taxation, and governmental approvals in numerous emerging nations. Weak institutional contexts have a negative impact on the growth of entrepreneurship, according to Gnyawali and Fogel (1994) in a similar vein, the World Bank (2023) notes that ineffective regulatory frameworks raise business expenses and hinder the expansion of small businesses.

Weak Government Assistance

For the starting of entrepreneurial journey, it needs governmental assistance in the shape of loans, entrepreneurial trainings and skill, policy and planning and centres where the students will be incubated. In many universities entrepreneurship skills learning programs are insufficient. According to Minniti (2008), government policies have a significant impact on entrepreneurial activity by influencing market opportunities and business conditions. Limited industrial policies and inadequate institutional infrastructure restrict the expansion of entrepreneurship in Balochistan.

Social and Cultural Limitations

Career decisions and risk-taking behavior are heavily influenced by social and cultural norms. Compared to government employment, entrepreneurship is viewed as unreliable in many nations. Graduates are frequently deterred from pursuing entrepreneurial endeavours by family pressure. According to Hayton et al. (2022), entrepreneurial activity and attitudes toward innovation and risk are shaped by cultural values. Social norms in conservative nations may discourage people from starting their own businesses, especially women.

Insufficient Market Prospects

New entrepreneurs have fewer business options due to poor market frameworks and little industrialization. Inadequate infrastructure, low purchasing power, and small local marketplaces limit the growth of businesses. Market access and the business climate are important factors that determine an entrepreneur's success, according to Storey (2016) Low investment and poor connection restrict business expansion in undeveloped areas.

Insufficient Digital and Technological Proficiency

Digital technologies, e-commerce, and internet marketing are becoming more and more important to modern entrepreneurship. However, a large number of graduates lack the technological knowledge and digital literacy required for competitive business operations. According to the World Bank (2023), while digital transformation opens up new business prospects, unequal access to technology and regional inequities. Digital entrepreneurship is further hampered by inadequate internet connectivity in remote areas.

Limited Business Support Systems and Social Networks

Business incubation centres, mentorship, and professional networks are beneficial to entrepreneurs. However, a lot of graduates without jobs are not exposed to networking possibilities and business ecosystems. According to Aldrich and Zimmer (1986), social networks are essential for gaining access to market possibilities, funding, and information. Inadequate networking systems limit the potential for innovation and entrepreneurial growth.

Unsuitable Curriculum and Insufficient Subjects

The lack of appropriate entrepreneurship-related courses in academic departments is another significant issue affecting entrepreneurship among recent graduates. Degree programs at many colleges prioritize theoretical knowledge above practical and market-oriented learning. Therefore, many students who had completed their higher education but they have not enhanced their entrepreneurial skills. Skills of entrepreneurship, start-up planning, economic management, computer and digital literacy for marketing are insufficient in many institutions

of Quetta, Balochistan. Fayolle and Gailly (2015) stated that the skills of entrepreneurship significantly expand scholar's confidence, creativity and entrepreneurial purpose. Any ways student's preparation for employment is reduced by a dire curriculum model and lack of incubation centres in institutions.

Similarly vain, Kuratko (2016) stated by the mean of skills, new and modern programs and business incubation centres are important in starting and developing entrepreneurial journey. As a result, when these opportunities are not available then Graduates look for traditional jobs instead of entrepreneurship opportunities. In Quetta many institutions are using out dated and old curriculum that are lack of the market demand for new start-ups. The problem of unemployed university graduates is likely more caused by that there are no specific courses in departments to be teach to the students during their studies. There are no internships for youth in business hubs, incubation centres and partnerships with industries for the development of the entrepreneurial journey of graduates. An additional major barrier among unemployed graduates is that when they starting their own businesses or start-ups so they are lack of subsidies, loans from banks and seed grants for a successful business start-up. Many unemployed graduates have very good business ideas but they cannot bring it to a real business start-up due to lack of seed grant money, loans from government and other non-governmental organizations and other funding programs.

Funding assistance and programs from private, governmental and non-governmental organizations are very much important in promoting entrepreneurial journey. Access to funding is a major problem for entrepreneurs. According to the OECD (2022) Many owners of the start-ups are unable to bring their business to a develop and running stage without funding assistance similarly vain, Minniti (2008) Stated that financial assistance for entrepreneurs as a seed grant money is very much important for their entrepreneurial journey. Specifically for youth and those do not have enough experience and knowledge in entrepreneurship. Many graduates rely on their own or their families' resources, which are frequently insufficient for starting long-lasting firms. Consequently, limited entrepreneurial engagement and on-going unemployment are caused by a shortage of grants. Innovation, economic expansion, and job creation all depend heavily on entrepreneurship. However, a number of obstacles prevent entrepreneurs in underdeveloped nations from starting and growing businesses. Financial, educational, institutional, and sociocultural obstacles deter unemployed graduates in Quetta from pursuing entrepreneurial endeavours.

Methodology

Descriptive type of research is used in the study. A structured questionnaire was developed, the researcher collected detailed data from unemployed graduates using a descriptive methodology. The findings are displayed as percentages, tables, charts and descriptive interpretation. Descriptive research is to present an accurate picture of current events while keeping variables constant. The sample size of 216 graduates was selected from all public sector universities of Quetta city. To ensure the participation from all three public sector universities, a proportionate stratified sampling method was allocated for sample size.

Purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used to select respondents from major public universities in Quetta. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used to code and analyse each questionnaire response.

Results and discussions

Table 1

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Valid %</i>
1.1 Considered Starting Business (<i>n</i>=216)			
Yes	88	40.7	40.7
No	128	59.3	59.3
1.2 Lack of Capital (<i>n</i>=216)			
Slight Barrier	55	25.5	25.5
Moderate Barrier	51	23.6	23.6
Major Barrier	51	23.6	23.6
Extreme Barrier	59	27.3	27.3
1.3 Lack of the Business Knowledge (<i>n</i>=216)			
Slight Barrier	50	23.1	23.1
Moderate Barrier	57	26.4	26.4
Major Barrier	49	22.7	22.7
Extreme Barrier	60	27.8	27.8

Source: Jan-Feb 2026

Business Start ups

The data in the table 1 (1.1) shows that 88 responders which are 40.7 Percent had started their own businesses, while majority 53.3 Percent had not considered business as a career option. The findings show that a number of the responders have started businesses but majority are still looking for traditional employment opportunities. This condition may be influenced by lack of entrepreneurial skills, lack of financial, fear of failure and lack of capital. Governmental organizations and non-governmental organizations should work for the awareness of entrepreneurship, trainings and funding as a seed grant money or loan for entrepreneurship.

Lack of Capital

To understand the perceptions of the respondents regarding the barrier, this is lack of capital. The results in the table 1 (1.2) show that 59 respondents which are 27.3 Percent considered lack of capital as an extreme barrier while 23.6 Percent identified as a major barrier and 23.6 Percent said as a Moderate barrier. Only 25.5 Percent of the responders identified as a slight barrier. The findings show that financial constraints among graduates are a significant problem preventing unemployed graduates from starting businesses. More than half of the graduates are viewed as an extreme barrier. Providing financial resources are very much important while starting businesses, providing loans, trainings seed grant money can significantly improve participation and starting entrepreneurship. These findings are

consistent with Fatoki and Chindoga (2011), who described that limited access to finance and capital significantly discourages graduates entrepreneurship ventures. Similarly, the OECD (2022) identified that insufficient financial resources is primary obstacle for entrepreneurship. Therefore, access to finance is very much important for successful entrepreneurship programs.

Lack of the Business Knowledge

The perceptions of the responders were analysed to understand about the knowledge of business or entrepreneurship.

The results in the table 1 (1.3) show 27.8 Percent of the respondents identified as lack of business knowledge as an extreme barrier, 27.7 Percent considered as major barrier. Furthermore, 26.4 Percent said as moderate barrier, 23.1 Percent viewed as slight barrier and 22.7 Percent identified as a major barrier. The findings indicate that not enough business knowledge is a major problem among unemployed graduates. Entrepreneurship needs skills related to marketing, planning, financing and management for successful start-ups. These findings are supported by Fayolle and Gailly (2015), who indicated that entrepreneurship education positively influences Entrepreneurial ventures. So, Universities must strengthen education for successful start-ups.

Table 2

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Valid %</i>
2.1 Lack of Collateral (<i>n=216</i>)			
Not A Barrier	53	24.5	24.5
Slight Barrier	43	19.9	19.9
Moderate Barrier	38	17.6	17.6
Major Barrier	40	18.5	18.5
Extreme Barrier	42	19.4	19.4
2.2 Complex Government Procedures (<i>n=216</i>)			
Not A Barrier	37	17.1	17.1
Slight Barrier	49	22.7	22.7
Moderate Barrier	48	22.2	22.2
Major Barrier	43	19.9	19.9
Extreme Barrier	39	18.1	18.1
2.3 Lack of Family Support (<i>n=216</i>)			
Not A Barrier	42	19.4	19.4
Slight Barrier	40	18.5	18.5
Moderate Barrier	40	18.5	18.5
Major Barrier	52	24.1	24.1
Extreme Barrier	42	19.4	19.4

Source: Jan-Feb 2026

Lack of Collateral

The role of collateral is examined among unemployed graduates to understand whether they are able to find collateral.

The data in the table 2 (2.1) shows that 24.5 Percent identified as not a barrier, 19.9 Percent considered as a slight barrier, 19.4 Percent viewed as an extreme barrier, 18.5 Percent as a major barrier and 17.6 Percent as a moderate barrier. The finding shows that for some graduate's collateral is not a significant problem and many said it is a major problem while receiving financial support. Collateral is required by banks and other organizations for loan. That graduates should have assets and resources. The findings suggest that government may give loans on only small business start-ups to further promote business and graduate's entrepreneurship funds may alleviate this problem.

Complex Government Procedures

The respondents' perceptions regarding government procedures while registering their businesses.

The results in table 2 (2.2) show that 22.7 Percent considered government procedures as a slight barrier, 22.2 Percent identified as moderate barrier, 19.9 Percent said as a major barrier, 18.1 Percent viewed as an extreme barrier and only 17.1 Percent considered as not a barrier. The finding indicates that administrative process of business registration and licensing are major obstacles for entrepreneurs because they will not have access to loan when their business is not registered.

Lack of Family Support

The lack of family support was examined to understand the influences of the family regarding starting entrepreneurship by graduates.

The data in the table 2 (2.3) shows that 24.1 Percent graduates were considered lack of family support as a major barrier, 19.4 Percent identified as an extreme barrier, 19.4 Percent of the responders regarded as not a barrier and 18.5 Percent of the responders considered as slight and moderate barrier. The finding indicates that family has a positive role in starting a business or entrepreneurship. Families are always providing emotional, financial and social support in starting a business but in Quetta city families are not accepting entrepreneurship as a career because they think that the education which graduates received from higher education is useless then, if graduates are starting entrepreneurship so this is there miss understanding, where it need public awareness by institutions to accept entrepreneurship as a career goal. These findings are consistent with Hayton et al. (2022) who indicated that cultural values and family influences significantly affect entrepreneurship programs.

Table 3

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Valid %</i>
3.1 Market Competition(<i>n</i>=216)			
Not A Barrier	40	18.5	18.5
Slight Barrier	52	24.1	24.1

Moderate Barrier	42	19.4	19.4
Major Barrier	35	16.2	16.2
Extreme Barrier	47	21.8	21.8
3.2 Access to Business Loan (n=216)			
Yes	76	35.2	35.2
No	140	64.8	64.8
3.3 Reason of no Loan Access (n=216)			
Not Applicable	76	35.2	35.2
No collateral	42	19.4	19.4
Do not know the process	42	19.4	19.4
Banks do not serve graduates	56	25.9	25.9

Source: Jan-Feb 2026

Market Competition

To analysed the perceptions of the respondents regarding market competition as a barrier to entrepreneurship.

The results in the table 3 (3.1) show that 24.1 Percent of the responders are identified as market competition as a slight barrier, 21.8 Percent of the graduates considered as an extreme barrier, 19.4 Percent are viewed as moderate barrier, while 18.5 Percent of the responders considered as not a barrier and 16.2 Percent of graduates said as a major barrier. The finding indicates that markets which are more competitive could make significant obstacles to the new entrepreneurs. Who have limited resources, budget and experience.so market competition is a significant problem to graduates who has started new businesses, and they need to get training about marketing.

Access to Business Loan

Access to business loan was examined among unemployed graduates to understand the availability of loans.

The data in the table 3 (3.2) shows that majority 140 respondents which are 64.8 Percent do not have access to business loans while 35.2 Percent of the respondents reported that we had access to business loans. The results show that most of the graduates are facing obstacles while getting loans for entrepreneurships. Banks are playing a vital role in supporting entrepreneurs. However, the limited access to loans observed in the study that youth are excluded from entrepreneurial trainings and financial supports.

Reason of no Loan Access

The data is analysed to understand the reasons that why graduates do not have access to loans.

The results in the table 3 (3.3) show that 25.9 Percent of the responders considered that banks are not serving graduates, 19.4 Percent of the graduates said that we do know

The process, additionally 19.4 Percent of the responders were lack of collateral and the remaining identified as not applicable because they had already access to loans. The findings

indicate that both informational and banks are not serving graduates to access to financing. Access to loans or seed grants is the significant obstacles. The government and non-government organizations should specifically launch a program to graduate youth and give trainings during their studies.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship is one of the best and effective solutions for decreasing graduates' unemployment. However, a number of obstacles prevent unemployed graduates from getting entrepreneurial education. Financial problems, lack of capital, lack loans, lack of collateral, complex government procedures, lack of family support and obstacles of market competitions are the most significant barriers faced by graduates. Entrepreneurship of graduates remains a significant problem among universities graduates in Quetta. Despite having higher educational degrees, many of the graduates facing obstacles while securing Entrepreneurship opportunities. Most of the graduates are facing obstacles while getting loans for entrepreneurships. Banks are not serving graduates to access to financing. The study indicated the financial problems among unemployed graduates the most significant obstacles. Many graduates have reported that we do not have access to loans for establishing our new businesses. Many of them reported that banks and other financial institutions are not supporting unemployed graduates which these problems restrict graduates for starting entrepreneurship journeys. Furthermore, the graduates are lack of entrepreneurship knowledge and skills and they have higher educational degrees but lack of practical entrepreneurship skills to start new businesses. Assess to incubation centres is also one of the major barriers to entrepreneurship. There is no any proper curriculum on entrepreneurship in every department. Social factors play a vital role on launching entrepreneurship. The study indicated that lack of family support and the preference of government jobs discouraged graduates to take the risk of entrepreneurship. All of the above barriers restrict graduates from establishing entrepreneurship as a career option and the obstacles are interconnected which limit the ability of graduates from starting entrepreneurship.

The study reveals that entrepreneurship can be an effective and alternative option for unemployed university graduates. Successful entrepreneurship initiatives required coordinated efforts from government, universities and financial institutions by removing the identified obstacles and create entrepreneurship opportunities for unemployed graduates.

Recommendations

- The government should vast the entrepreneurship education particularly for students and graduates. Considerable efforts must be made to improve existing initiatives through universities, outreach sessions and social media.
- Government should release Specific funds for graduates and student's entrepreneurship journey. Resilient financing policies should be introduced to reduced collateral requirements.

- The higher education commission should publish incubation centres in every university where students will get training on mentorship, business skills, marketing and technical support for running a successful business.
- Universities should collaborate with governmental, non-governmental organizations and industry organizations to provide internships and work-based learning opportunities for graduates and students.
- The government should sign partnerships with Banks for easy access of loans.
- The government and universities should conduct awareness sessions for graduates and communities for the importance of entrepreneurship.
- The Higher Education Commission should align the curriculum with entrepreneurship.
- Universities should make a monitoring and evaluation team for the promotion of entrepreneurship.

References

- Acs, Z. J., Audretsch, D. B., Lehmann, E. E., & Licht, G. (2018). National systems of entrepreneurship. *Small Business Economics*, 46(4), 527–535.
- Aldrich, H., & Zimmer, C. (1986). Entrepreneurship through social networks. In D. Sexton & R. Smilor (Eds.), *The Art and Science of Entrepreneurship* (pp. 3–23). Ballinger.
- Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship: Practice and principles*. Harper & Row.
- Fatoki, O., & Chindoga, L. (2011). An investigation into the obstacles to youth entrepreneurship in South Africa. *International Business Research*, 4(2), 161–169.
- Fayolle, A., & Gailly, B. (2015). The impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial attitudes and intention. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(1), 75–93.
- Gnyawali, D. R., & Fogel, D. S. (1994). Environments for entrepreneurship development: Key dimensions and research implications. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 18(4), 43–62.
- Haque, M. (2021). Youth entrepreneurship and economic development in Pakistan. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 10(2), 45–58.
- Hayton, J. C., George, G., & Zahra, S. A. (2022). National culture and entrepreneurship. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 26(4), 33–52.
- Kew, J., Herrington, M., Litovsky, Y., & Gale, H. (2013). Generation entrepreneur? The state of global youth entrepreneurship. *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor*.
- Kuratko, D. F. (2016). *Entrepreneurship: Theory, Process, and Practice* (10th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Minniti, M. (2008). The role of government policy on entrepreneurial activity: Productive, unproductive, or destructive? *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 32(5), 779–790.

- Nabi, G., Liñán, F., Fayolle, A., Krueger, N., & Walmsley, A. (2017). The impact of entrepreneurship education in higher education: A systematic review and research agenda. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 16(2), 277–299.
- Nabi, G., Liñán, F., Fayolle, A., Krueger, N., & Walmsley, A. (2018). The impact of entrepreneurship education in higher education: A systematic review and research agenda. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 17(2), 277–299.
- Naudé, W. (2010). Entrepreneurship, developing countries, and development economics: New approaches and insights. *Small Business Economics*, 34(1), 1–12.
- Nawaz, A. (2021). Entrepreneurship education and graduate employability in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Education*, 38(1), 89–104.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2022). *Financing SMEs and Entrepreneurs 2022: An OECD Scoreboard*. OECD Publishing. Pakistan Bureau of Statistics.
- (2023). Labour force survey 2022–23. Government of Pakistan.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1934). *The theory of economic development*. Harvard University Press.
- State Bank of Pakistan. (2021). Annual report 2020–21. State Bank of Pakistan.
- Storey, D. J. (2016). *Understanding the small business sector* (1st ed.). Routledge.
- World Bank. (2020). World development report 2020: Trading for development in the age of global value chains. World Bank.
- World Bank. (2023). World Development Report 2023. Washington, DC: World Bank.